

Side-chain Alkylation of Toluene with Methanol over Dual Catalysts comprising X-Zeolites and Fe-Mo Oxide

N. K. DAS* and KRISHNA PRAMANIK

Department of Chemical Technology, University Colleges of Science & Technology, Calcutta University, 92 A. P. C. Road, Calcutta-700 009

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The activities of various dual catalyst systems consisting of Na-X, Cs-X and Cs-B-X alongwith Fe-Mo oxide catalyst have been investigated towards side-chain alkylation reactions of toluene with methanol at atmospheric pressure in a fixed-bed reactor. Among these Cs-X/Fe-Mo dual catalyst showed the highest activity and selectivity leading to a maximum toluene conversion of 33.1% and a styrene-to-ethylbenzene mole ratio of 10 : 1 under optimum reaction conditions such as at 425° and toluene-to-methanol mole ratio of 1 : 5. The activities of all the single zeolites were improved by utilising Fe-Mo oxide in the dual catalyst systems.

The single zeolite catalysts, such as Na-X, Cs-X and Cs-B-X already studied by us¹ show side-chain alkylation activity to a varied extent. Among the catalysts studied, Cs-X had been found to be most active. However, though the conversion of toluene and yields and selectivities to side-chain alkylation products were good, the activity of the catalyst needed to be improved in order to make it more effective from the point of view of eventual industrial use of such a catalyst.

A very important consideration for styrene production in one-step through the alkylation of toluene side-chain is the yield of ethylbenzene alongwith styrene. Ethylbenzene is always a co-product of this reaction as has been shown in our previous study¹ and studies by other workers². Formation of considerable quantities of ethylbenzene alongwith styrene has been one of the disadvantage of this one-step styrene synthetic process. This would necessitate further conversion of the ethylbenzene to styrene through the classical dehydrogenation route. In that case the proposed one-step synthesis of styrene through the side-chain alkylation of toluene with methanol would lose much of its novelty and can hardly offer an alternative and cheaper route to styrene manufacture. Hence it is important to keep the ethylbenzene as low as possible and maximise styrene formation. This important aspect, however, has received little attention in the work published so far.

Since formaldehyde formation is known³⁻⁵ to be a key factor in the side-chain alkylation reaction of toluene with methanol, attempts have been made to facilitate the decomposition of methanol to formaldehyde by several workers^{4,6}. Lacroix *et al.*⁵ employed a dual catalyst system of Cu or Ag alongwith Cs-X and Cs-B-X zeolites with the intention to increase the formaldehyde concentration and eventual higher side-chain alkylation activity of the dual catalysts. Though side-chain alkylation activity was found to increase considerably with the dual catalysts employed but the end-product contained almost exclusively ethylbenzene with very little or no styrene. This is contrary to the expectation for achieving the desirable effect of increasing

the styrene yield in the reaction product.

Therefore, in the present study, efforts have been made to increase the styrene selectivity without concomitant increase of ethylbenzene formation. In this attempt the side-chain alkylation reaction of toluene with methanol was studied by employing the dual catalyst systems consisting of Na-X, Cs-X and Cs-B-X zeolites alongwith Fe-Mo oxide catalyst as promoter. The Fe-Mo oxide catalyst was employed to facilitate the formation of formaldehyde in the alkylation reaction since it is known to be a very effective catalyst for the commercial manufacture of formaldehyde from methanol.

Results and Discussion

In the present investigation side-chain alkylations of toluene with methanol were carried out on the above dual catalysts in a fixed-bed reactor under varying mole ratios of reactants (toluene : methanol = 5 : 1 to 1 : 5) and in the temperature range 325–450° at atmospheric pressure. The other reaction conditions were maintained constant throughout the experiment as reported in our previous work¹.

Reaction temperature : The effectivity of dual catalyst was studied at a constant toluene : methanol mole ratio of 1 : 5 in the temperature range 325–450°. The results (Table 1) indicated that the alkylation reaction took place at 325° and the activity of the catalysts increased steadily with the rise in temperature as was evidenced by the steady increase in conversion of toluene and yield of styrene. However, in agreement with the previous findings^{1,7}, 425° was found the most suitable reaction temperature in relation to the yield of styrene as well as retention of the catalyst activity with time-on-stream. At 450°, a slight increase in toluene conversion and styrene yield was obtained but the catalyst activity decreased rapidly with time-on-stream due to carbon deposition on the surface of the catalysts. Styrene selectivity remained almost constant beyond 375° with Cs-X/Fe-Mo and Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo dual catalysts. Though selectivity was a bit complicated with

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF REACTION TEMPERATURE ON SIDE-CHAIN ALKYLATION OF TOLUENE WITH DUAL CATALYSTS*

	Na-X/Fe-Mo						Cs-X/Fe-Mo						Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo					
	325°	350°	375°	400°	425°	450°	325°	350°	375°	400°	425°	450°	325°	350°	375°	400°	425°	450°
Conv. (mol %):																		
Toluene	1.4	3.33	6.4	8.3	10.0	10.85	9.83	16.1	22.5	28.0	33.5	34.5	8.0	14.6	19.15	24.6	30.7	32.12
Yield (mole %):																		
Styrene	0.75	0.7	3.25	4.5	5.83	6.20	8.33	14.2	20.0	25.0	30.0	30.8	6.7	12.5	16.7	21.7	27.08	28.33
Ethylbenzene	0.70	1.6	3.0	3.7	4.16	4.5	1.3	1.67	2.08	2.6	2.9	3.08	1.2	1.83	2.2	2.5	3.08	3.25
% Selectivity:																		
Styrene	52.9	51.3	52.0	55.1	58.3	57.8	86.2	89.5	90.6	90.6	90.6	90.9	85.1	87.2	88.5	89.6	89.8	89.7
Ethylbenzene	47.06	48.7	48	44.9	41.6	42.2	13.8	10.5	9.4	9.4	9.4	9.1	14.9	12.8	11.5	10.4	10.2	10.3

*Toluene : methanol mole ratio = 1 : 5.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF MOLECULAR RATIOS OF TOLUENE-TO-METHANOL ON SIDE CHAIN ALKYLATION OF TOLUENE WITH DUAL CATALYSTS*

	Na-X/Fe-Mo					Cs-X/Fe-Mo					Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo				
	5:1	3:1	1:1	1:3	1:5	5:1	3:1	1:1	1:3	1:5	5:1	3:1	1:1	1:3	1:5
Conv. (mole %):															
Toluene	—	—	4.7	7.63	10.0	—	—	18.75	27.12	33.5	—	—	17.4	25.17	30.7
Methanol	1.6	2.96	—	—	—	9.6	14.9	—	—	—	8.22	13.15	—	—	—
Yield (mole %):															
Styrene	0.75	1.43	2.5	4.16	5.83	8.17	12.0	16.66	24.1	30.0	6.95	11.2	15.0	22.08	27.08
Ethylbenzene	0.708	1.4	2.16	3.33	4.16	1.08	1.67	2.08	2.5	2.92	0.9	1.64	2.08	2.7	3.08
Benzene	0.038	0.05	—	—	—	0.148	0.092	—	—	—	0.04	0.046	—	—	—
Xylenes	0.042	0.042	—	—	—	0.141	0.10	—	—	—	0.036	0.04	—	—	—
% Selectivity:															
Styrene	51.43	50.6	53.6	55.55	58.33	88.5	88	88.9	90.6	91.1	87.2	86.8	87.8	89.23	89.8
Ethylbenzene	48.57	49.4	46.4	44.44	41.66	11.5	12	11.1	9.4	8.9	12.8	13.2	12.2	10.77	10.2

*Reaction temp. = 425°.

Na-X/Fe-Mo dual catalyst, the maximum selectivity was obtained at 425°.

Molecular ratios of reactants: The effect of mole ratios of reactants on the side-chain alkylation of toluene with methanol on the various dual catalysts employed in the present paper was examined at the mole ratio of toluene : methanol from 5 : 1 to 1 : 5 at 425°. The results are shown in Table 2. At higher toluene : methanol, the yields of products were very low and traces of benzene and xylenes were formed due to disproportionation of toluene. With decrease in toluene : methanol ratio, there was an increase in side-chain alkylation reactions leading to higher yields of styrene and ethylbenzene and also no side-reactions were found to take place. Thus the reactions proceeded best at higher methanol : toluene ratio of 5 : 1.

Activities and selectivity of dual catalysts: In this present work, efforts have been made to increase the styrene selectivity without concomitant increase of ethylbenzene formation by employing various dual catalysts as mentioned earlier. The activity and selectivity of the above catalysts under optimum condition are shown in Table 3. The results were quite encouraging as these dual catalyst systems effected a better yield of side-chain alkylated products with a higher styrene selectivity, while the yield and selectivity of ethylbenzene decreased to a considerable extent for all the catalysts employed. Further, highest yield and selectivity of styrene was obtained with Cs-X/Fe-Mo

catalyst and Na-X/Fe-Mo was found to be least active. The activity of Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo was slightly less as exemplified by the lower yield ratio of styrene-to-ethylbenzene about 8.8 : 1 compared to 10 : 1 with Cs-X/Fe-Mo catalyst.

From the effect of mole ratio of reactants and reaction temperature (Tables 1 and 2), it was observed that Cs-X/Fe-Mo dual catalyst was more active than the other two dual catalysts under all conditions of reactions. Thus the activities of dual catalyst systems for the side-chain alkylation of toluene with methanol decreased in the following sequence : Cs-X/Fe-Mo > Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo > Na-X/Fe-Mo.

Activity of single Fe-Mo oxide catalyst: The effectivity of Fe-Mo oxide catalyst for side-chain alkylation of toluene with methanol was examined by conducting alkylation experiments with the above catalyst alone under all reaction conditions as has been mentioned earlier. There was no formation of side-chain alkylation products, viz. styrene and ethylbenzene, also benzene or xylenes were not detected as side-products even at trace levels. This clearly indicates that Fe-Mo does not take part either in side-chain alkylation or any undesired side-reactions such as disproportionation of toluene.

Comparison of the activities of single and dual catalysts: Several similar points have been observed in the side-chain alkylation of toluene over single and dual

Fig. 1. Change of activity with time-on-stream over Cs-X/Fe-Mo catalyst : (●) toluene, (Δ) styrene, (○) ethylbenzene; reaction temp. = 425°.

catalyst systems. In both cases, the optimum reaction temperature is 425° and the reactions proceed best at 1 : 5 of toluene : methanol mole ratio. Furthermore, the single Cs-X and Cs-B-X zeolites as well as dual catalysts, viz. Cs-X/Fe-Mo and Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo show a fairly good stability with time-on-stream. On the other hand, as can be seen from Table 3, the dual catalysts were found to be more effective than the corresponding single zeolites with respect to higher yields and conversions as well as higher styrene : ethylbenzene mole ratio with dual catalysts. Also, the dual catalysts were active at comparatively lower

Fig. 2. Change of activity with time-on-stream over Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo catalyst : (●) toluene, (Δ) styrene, (○) ethylbenzene; reaction temp. = 425°, toluene : methanol mole ratio = 1 : 5.

temperature than single zeolites as exemplified by the activity shown by the dual catalyst at 325°, whereas no sig-

nificant activity was observed with single zeolites even at 375°. Further, Na-X zeolite did not show the desired side-chain alkylation activity either singly or as a dual catalyst system containing Fe-Mo oxide catalyst.

Change in the catalyst activity : In alkylation experiments, the activities of the Cs-X/Fe-Mo and Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo dual catalysts were studied over a period of time by observing the changes in the yields of side-chain alkylation products as well as toluene conversion under optimum reaction conditions. From the results (Figs. 1 and 2) it was observed that the catalysts were active without any pronounced change in yield and conversion upto 7 h. Compared to Cs-X/Fe-Mo, slightly better performance was obtained with Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo dual catalyst as was evidenced by the little change of toluene conversion (30.7 to 29.5%) and styrene yield (27.08 to 26.02%) with the latter at 1 and 7 h respectively. However, after 7 h. there was slow but steady loss of activity with time of both the catalysts due to carbon deposition on the surface of catalysts. The catalysts could be regenerated by burning off the deposited carbon with oxygen and reused.

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF ACTIVITIES OF SINGLE AND DUAL CATALYSTS FOR THE SIDE-CHAIN ALKYLATION OF TOLUENE*

Catalyst	Toluene conv. (mole %)	Yield (mole %)		% Selectivity	
		Styrene	Ethylbenzene	Styrene	Ethylbenzene
Na-X	8.2	4.2	3.5	54.3	45.7
Cs-X	25.5	20.0	5.08	79.7	20.3
Cs-B-X	25.1	19.2	5.7	77.2	22.8
Na-X/Fe-Mo	10.0	5.83	4.16	58.33	41.66
Na-X/Fe-Mo	33.5	30.0	2.92	90.6	9.4
Cs-B-X/Fe-Mo	30.7	27.08	3.08	89.8	10.2

*Reaction temp. = 425°; toluene : methanol mole ratio = 1 : 5.

Experimental

Synthesis grade toluene and methanol (99% purity, E. Merck) were used.

Catalyst preparation : Cs-X zeolite containing 10.97 wt% Cs was prepared by ion-exchange of molecular sieve 13 X with cesium hydroxide solution and then modified with boron as promoter to obtain Cs-B-X zeolite catalyst containing 0.8 wt% B following reported procedure¹.

The iron-molybdenum (Fe-Mo) oxide catalyst as the dual catalyst component, was prepared by the reported method⁸. The oxide catalyst was prepared by using ferric chloride and ammonium heptamolybdate. The iron-hydroxide precipitate obtained by adding an aqueous ammonia solution to aqueous ferric chloride solution, was washed with distilled water. Required amounts of an aqueous ammonium heptamolybdate solution was added to the precipitate and mixed thoroughly followed by drying at 110° in an air-oven for 24 h and calcining at 550° for 6 h to get the corresponding oxide catalyst with 6.38 : 2.22 wt ratio of Fe/Mo.

Procedures for catalyst testing and product analysis were the same as reported earlier¹.

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